

Synthetic Data Generation for Wastewater Digital Twin Calibration Using SUMO and Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT

Digital twins are emerging as a foundation for the intelligent operation of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). These systems combine simulation, data analytics, and real-time monitoring to support optimisation and predictive control. By virtually replicating biological and hydraulic behaviour, digital twins enable operators to test different scenarios, predict failures, and optimise aeration or pumping strategies without interfering with plant performance. However, as highlighted by Wang et al. (2024) [1], the construction of robust WWTP digital twins is often hindered by data scarcity and fragmentation, since most treatment facilities lack continuous, high-quality datasets covering the dynamic operation of all process stages. To fill this gap, synthetic data generated through mechanistic simulation offers a reproducible and privacy-safe pathway to train, calibrate, and validate machine learning (ML) models, which can further serve as real-time surrogates for complex process units.

This work investigates the use of SUMO, a process simulation environment for biological wastewater treatment, to produce synthetic datasets capable of representing the dynamic response of WWTP units. The main goal is to evaluate whether SUMO-based synthetic data can effectively substitute limited field measurements for ML model calibration and validation. The primary objective is to establish a systematic workflow for integrating simulation, ML, and explainability into a hybrid digital twin architecture.

The aeration system is first simulated in SUMO [2], comprising multiple blowers, air-distribution manifolds, and an aeration tank with variable oxygen demand. Process variables such as air flowrate, valve openings, dissolved oxygen (DO), and energy consumption are recorded under multiple operational scenarios. These scenarios simulate both steady-state and transient dynamics (e.g., diurnal inflow variation, setpoint disturbances, and control feedbacks). The simulated time series are then used to train a set of regression-based ML models, each corresponding to a specific process purpose, for example, aeration dynamics, or energy consumption.

Figure 1 illustrates the parallelism between the physical aeration system and its virtual ML model. To replicate the dynamics occurring within the aeration tank, the ML model must receive the same type of inputs and generate equivalent outputs. In the physical system, multiple blowers deliver air at variable flow rates to the aeration basins, with airflow sometimes regulated by control valves. Sensors measuring parameters such as temperature and total suspended solids (TSS)

provide the data streams used as ML model inputs. By learning the nonlinear interactions among these variables, the ML module can reproduce and predict the dissolved-oxygen (O_2) behaviour within the tank, effectively serving as a computational proxy of the real process. Once validated, this ML models can be embedded within optimisation or control layers to test aeration strategies and assess energy savings potential. Ultimately, this methodology provides a replicable route to develop digital twins even in plants with limited instrumentation or data-sharing restrictions.

Figure 1. Illustrative example of a ML to simulate aeration process

To approximate real-world conditions, Gaussian and autoregressive noise are added to the synthetic signals to reproduce typical sensor errors observed in SCADA systems. This approach follows the concept introduced in [3], where synthetic data was used to pre-train reinforcement-learning controllers for wastewater pumps, enabling learning without physical system interaction. Similarly, in this study, the SUMO-generated datasets act as a “virtual plant” for ML pre-training, allowing rapid prototyping of models before their fine-tuning with limited real data.

Model performance is evaluated through k-fold cross-validation using root-mean-square error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination (R^2). Transferability is assessed by applying the synthetic-trained models to small subsets of measured WWTP data. To ensure interpretability, feature importance and partial-dependence analyses are conducted to verify that learned relationships (e.g., between airflow and DO) were physically consistent. The workflow is designed to be easily generalisable to other WWTP units such as clarifiers or sludge treatment lines.

Recent studies, such as [4] have demonstrated the power of hybrid models combining mechanistic and ML approaches to improve predictive accuracy and reduce calibration effort in activated-sludge systems. Yet, few studies have addressed the methodological challenge of how to generate and validate synthetic data to bootstrap ML model development. The novelty of this work lies in proposing a structured synthetic-data-driven calibration pipeline, where the mechanistic simulator acts as a physics-based knowledge generator and the ML surrogate functions as a fast-responding component within the digital twin. The

framework thus contributes to the transition from black-box ML toward transparent, hybrid, and transferable digital twins for data-limited WWTPs.

The proposed SUMO–ML integration offers a robust path to develop and calibrate digital-twin components for WWTPs using purely synthetic datasets. It reduces dependency on plant-specific data, ensures reproducibility, and supports scalable deployment of explainable ML surrogates. Future work will focus on extending the approach to multi-stage WWTP models and integrating uncertainty quantification and active-learning mechanisms to refine model calibration with minimal real-data feedback.

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